

A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFECT OF ARKA KADALI PRATISARANIYA KSHARA KARMA AND APAMARGA PRATISARANIYA KSHARA KARMA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF ABHYANTARA ARSHAS VIS-À-VIS INTERNAL HAEMORRHOIDS

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Arshas* is a protrusion of *Mamsa* which obstructs the *Gudamarga* and afflict the person like an enemy. *Acharya* considered it under *Ashtamahagada* because its *Deergakalanubandi* and *Dushchikitsya* nature, as it is occurring in *Guda* which is one among the *Sadyopranahara Marma*. Due to *Aharaja*, *Viharaja* and *Manasika Nidan*, *Agni* become *Manda* thus aggravates the *Doshas*. The aggravated *Doshas* enters *Guda*, vitiates *Gudavalis* to form *Mamsapraroha* called as *Arshas*. In contemporary science it can be correlated to Haemorrhoids. Haemorrhoids are the dilated veins within the anal canal in sub-epithelial region formed by radicles of superior, middle and inferior rectal veins. *Acharya* has mentioned four treatment modalities for *Arshas*, one among them is *Kshara Karma*. The *Kshara* is considered as *Shreshta*, as it does the functions of *Chedana*, *Bhedana* and *Lekhana karma*, which is used in *Mridu*, *Prasrita*, *Avagada* and *Uchrita Arshas*. *Arka* has *Vranaropana*, *Vranashodana*, *Kandughna*, *Kaphashamana*, *Arshogna* properties. *Kadali Kanda* has *Kaphapittahara*, *Rakatashamaka* properties. The present study was designed to assess the combined efficacy of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* in *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis* Internal haemorrhoids. **Methods:** 40 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria of *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis* Internal haemorrhoids was randomly selected from OPD and IPD of *Shalyatantra*, teaching hospital attached to G.A.M. C, Bengaluru and is divided into 2 groups i.e., Group A and Group B comprising of 20 patients in each group. In Group A: *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma*, In Group B: *Apamarga Pratisaraniya kshara Karma* was done. The parameters were observed based on assessment criteria and recorded. **Result:** The p-value of 0.82 is greater than significance level of 0.05, indicating that there is no statistically significant difference between Group A and Group B in terms of their overall response. **Conclusion:** *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* is as effective as *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* in the management of *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis* Internal Haemorrhoids.

KEYWORDS: *Abhyantara Arshas*, Internal Haemorrhoids, *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma*.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus comprises group of metabolic disorders, with an increasing incidence worldwide.^[1] Foot ulcers and infections are also a major source of morbidity in individuals with DM. The reasons for the increased incidence of these disorders in DM involve the interaction of several pathogenic factors: neuropathy,

abnormal foot biomechanics, peripheral arterial disease, and poor wound healing.^[2] The peripheral sensory neuropathy interferes with normal protective mechanisms and allows the patient to sustain major or repeated minor trauma to the foot, often without knowledge of the injury. Disordered proprioception causes abnormal weight bearing while walking and

subsequent formation of callus or ulceration. Motor and sensory neuropathy lead to abnormal foot muscle mechanics and to structural changes in the foot (hammer toe, claw toe deformity, prominent metatarsal heads, Charcot joint). Approximately 15% of individuals with DM develop a foot ulcer, and a significant subset will ultimately undergo amputation (14 to 24% risk with that ulcer or subsequent ulceration). Risk factors for foot ulcers or amputation include: male sex, diabetes -10 years' duration, peripheral neuropathy, abnormal structure of foot (bony abnormalities, callus), peripheral arterial disease, smoking, history of previous ulcer or amputation, and poor glycemic control.^[3]

The management of DFUs is complex and requires a multidisciplinary approach. Optimal glycaemic control, wound debridement, and suitable dressings, infection management with appropriate antibiotics, revascularization, amputation.^[4] Therapeutic modalities such as negative pressure wound therapy, hyperbaric oxygen therapy, engineered skin allograft substitute, use of local growth factors have shown promising results in enhancing wound healing.^[5] Despite these advancements, DFUs remain a major cause of lower-limb amputation, emphasizing the need for effective, accessible, and cost-efficient treatment strategies.

In Ayurveda, diabetic foot ulcers can be correlated with *Madhumehajanya Dushta Vrana*. Acharya *Sushruta*, described *Shashti Upakrama* - sixty therapeutic measures for the management of various types of *Vrana*, incorporating both local and systemic interventions.^[6] These principles emphasize wound cleansing, healing promotion, and tissue regeneration. The present case study aims to explore the role of Ayurvedic management in the treatment of a diabetic foot ulcer, highlighting its potentiality as a cost-effective outpatient-based therapeutic approach.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- To evaluate the effect of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara karma* in the management of *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis Internal Haemorrhoids*
- To evaluate the effect of *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara karma* in the management of *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis Internal Haemorrhoids*
- To compare the effect of *Arka Kadali* and *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara karma* in the management of *Abhyantara Arshas vis-à-vis Internal Haemorrhoids*.

HYPOTHESIS

H₀-There is no significant difference between the effect of *Arka Kadali and Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* in management of *Abhyantara Arsha vis-a-vis Internal haemorrhoids*.

H₁-There is significant effect of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* in management of *Abhyantara Arsha vis-a-vis Internal haemorrhoids*.

H₂-There is significant effect of *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* in management of *Abhyantara Arsha vis-a-vis Internal haemorrhoids*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Source Of Data

- A. **Literary source:** *Ayurveda* Classical Texts, Modern textbooks, Journals & authenticated Websites.
- B. **Sample source**-40 Patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria, was selected for the study from OPD and IPD of Dept. of *Shalyatantra*, teaching hospital attached to G.A.M.C., Bengaluru was selected for the study. The study was conducted from Jan 2024-Sep 2025.
- C. **Drug source** -The identified raw drugs required for the clinical study were purchased from approved vendors. Procured drugs are checked for the genuinely in the department of *Dravya guna* and the formulation was prepared in the Department of *Rasa Shastra* and *Bhaishajya Kalpana* of GAMC, Bengaluru.

Methods of collection of data

D. Study Design

A Randomized open label clinical study was conducted.

E. Sampling technique

The subjects who fulfil the inclusion criteria and complying with the informed consent (IC) were selected using method of Computerized Randomization Table.

F. Sample Size

Subjects diagnosed with *Abhyantara Arshas* of both the gender were randomly assigned into two Groups, Group A and Group B comprising of 20 Subjects each. A special case proforma containing all the necessary details pertaining to the study was prepared.

A) INCLUSION CRITERIA

- Patient above 18 and below 60 years of age.
- Haemorrhoids which are *Mridu, Prasrita, Uchrita, Avaghada*.
- Patients with clinical features of 1st and 2nd degree haemorrhoids, mass per anum, Bleeding per anum, Pruritus ani and mucoid discharge per anum

B) EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Associated with other diseases like *Condyloma acuminata* and *Condyloma lata*, *Ulcerative colitis*.
- Pregnancy and Lactating women
- Faecal incontinence
- Known case of Hepatitis B & HIV I and II
- Uncontrolled Diabetes mellitus type 1 and 2 and HTN
- Contraindicated for *Kshara Karma*

❖ INTERVENTION

A total of 40 Subjects of internal haemorrhoids, those fulfilling the above criteria were included for the study

and randomly allotted into 2 groups namely Group-A & Group-B with 20 patients each.

GROUP A	GROUP B
<i>Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma in Abhyantara Arsha.</i>	<i>Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma in Abhyantara Arsha.</i>

PROCEDURE OF KSHARAKARMA

PRE-OPERATIVE PROCEDURE

Informed written consent was taken, part preparation done, Vitals recorded, Inj. T.T 0.5 ml IM was given, Inj. xylocaine test dose 0.1cc was given subcutaneously, Sodium phosphate 100 ml enema was given. Clearance of bowel confirmed then patient was shifted to operation theatre.

OPERATIVE PROCEDURE

Patient was made to lie down in lithotomy position. The surgical area was painted with a povidone iodine solution followed by surgical spirit and then draped with hole towel. Local anaesthesia was infiltrated with inj. Lignocaine 2% after calculating maximum dose according to weight. Surgical procedure was started after confirming effect of anaesthesia. Manual anal dilatation was done. Lubricated proctoscope was introduced. Haemorrhoidal mass and their position are noted. Slit proctoscope was introduced respective to position of haemorrhoidal mass, skin around haemorrhoidal mass was retracted with Alli's tissue holding forceps to get a better view of haemorrhoids. The anal mucosa around the haemorrhoidal mass was covered with wet gauze piece to prevent spilling of *kshara* on it. Haemorrhoidal mass was gently scraped with the serrations over BP handle. Then *Nakhaotshedha pramana* of *Arka Kadali kshara* / *Apamarga kshara* was applied over haemorrhoidal mass and opening of proctoscope was closed for *Shata Matra Kala* with the palm. Haemorrhoidal mass was observed for the change in colour from reddish-pink to bluish- black (*Pakwa Jambu Phala Varna*). If the *Pakwa jambu Phala Varna* is not observed, same procedure is repeated again. *Kshara* was washed with vinegar followed by normal saline. Same procedure was followed if other haemorrhoidal mass present. Slit proctoscope and wet gauze piece were removed from anal canal after the procedure. An anal pack prepared by smearing with povidone-iodine, 2% lignocaine gel, and *Yashtimadhu Ghritha*. Sterile dressing was done. Vitals recorded post operatively and patient was shifted to ward.

POST OPERATIVE PROCEDURE

Anal pack was removed after 6 hours. Analgesic drug was administered according to the need. From Post operative day 1 patient was advised *Panchavalkala Kwatha* sitz bath for 15 minutes twice daily. 20 ml of *Yashtimadhu Ghritha* was administered from anal route for 7 days, *Triphala Churna* in dose of 1 tsp was given at bedtime with lukewarm water as laxative. *Triphala Guggulu* 1-1-1 A/F, *Gandhaka Rasayana* 1-1-1 A/F, Patients were advised to take fibre rich diet.

ASSESSMENT CRITERIA

observation regarding changes were observed on 0,1ST 7th, 14th and 21st day and the same is recorded.

BLEEDING PER ANUM (RAKTA SRAVA)

GRADE	BLEEDING PER ANUM
0	No bleeding
1	Bleeding only during defecation
2	Bleeding during and after defecation
3	Bleeding irrespective of defecation

PRURITUS ANI (GUDA KANDU)

GRADE	PRURITUS ANI
0	Pruritus ani absent
1	Pruritus ani present

MUCOID DISCHARGE PER ANUM (GUDA SRAVA).

GRADE	DISCHARGE PER ANUM
0	Discharge absent
1	Discharge present

PILE MASS (ARSHANKURA)

GRADE	PILE MASS
0	Pile mass absent
1	Pile mass present

OVERALL RESPONSE

CLASS	GRADING
<24%	Poor Response
25-49%	Moderate Response
50-74%	Good Response
75-100%	Excellent Response

Investigation: CBC, ESR, CT, BT, RBS, HIV, HBsAg are done.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE: Ethical clearance obtained from the Institutional ethics committee of Government ayurveda medical college, Bengaluru.

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

1) BLEEDING PER ANUM

Table no - 1: Effect of treatment on Bleeding per Anum within Group A.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	4.10
D1	3.35
D7	2.60
D14	2.48
D21	2.48

a. Groups = Group A	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	39.636
Df	4
P value	0.000
a. Groups = Group A	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 2: Effect of treatment on Bleeding per Anum within Group B.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	4.05
D1	3.55
D7	2.55
D14	2.43
D21	2.43
a. Groups = Group B	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	41.486
Df	4
P value	.000
a. Groups = Group B	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 3: Effect of treatment on Bleeding per Anum between Group A & B.

Test Statistics ^a					
	BT	D1	D7	D14	D21
Mann-Whitney U	200.000	180.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Wilcoxon W	410.000	390.000	410.000	410.000	410.000
Z	0.000	-.637	0.000	0.000	0.000
P value (2-tailed)	1.000	.524	1.000	1.000	1.000
a. Grouping Variable: Groups					
b. Not corrected for ties.					

Since p values > 0.05, the level of significance; there is no evidence to reject null hypothesis.

2) PRURITUS ANI

Table no 4: Effect of treatment on pruritic ani within Group A.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.45
D1	3.45
D7	2.95
D14	2.58
D21	2.58
a. Groups = Group A	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	23.429
Df	4
P value	.000
a. Groups = Group A	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 5: Effect of treatment on pruritus ani within Group B.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.38
D1	3.38
D7	3.00
D14	2.63
D21	2.63
a. Groups = Group B	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	18.000
Df	4
P value	.001
a. Groups = Group B	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 6: Effect of treatment on pruritus ani between Group A & Group B.

Test Statistics ^a					
	BT	D1	D7	D14	D21
Mann-Whitney U	190.000	190.000	200.000	200.000	200.000
Wilcoxon W	400.000	400.000	410.000	410.000	410.000
Z	-.333	-.333	0.000	0.000	0.000
P value (2-tailed)	.739	.739	1.000	1.000	1.000
a. Grouping Variable: Groups					
b. Not corrected for ties.					

Since p values > 0.05, the level of significance; there is no evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

3) MUCOID DISCHARGE PER ANUM**Table no 7: Effect of treatment on Mucoïd discharge per Anum within Group A.**

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.25
D1	3.25
D7	3.00
D14	2.75
D21	2.75
a. Groups = Group A	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	13.333
Df	4
P value	.010
a. Groups = Group A	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 8: Effect of treatment on Mucoïd discharge per Anum within Group B.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.63
D1	3.38
D7	2.75
D14	2.63
D21	2.63
a. Groups = Group B	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	25.455
Df	4
P value	.000
a. Groups = Group B	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 9: Treatment on Mucoïd discharge per Anum between Group A & B.

Test Statistics ^a					
	BT	D1	D7	D14	D21
Mann-Whitney U	160.000	180.000	190.000	200.000	200.000
Wilcoxon W	370.000	390.000	400.000	410.000	410.000
Z	-1.363	-.721	-.593	0.000	0.000
P value (2-tailed)	.173	.471	.553	1.000	1.000
a. Grouping Variable: Groups					
b. Not corrected for ties.					

Since p values > 0.05, the level of significance; there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

4) PILE MASS**Table no 10: Effect of treatment on pile mass within Group A.**

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.25
D1	3.25
D7	3.25
D14	3.25
D21	2.00
a. Groups = Group A	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	40.000
Df	4

P value	.000
a. Groups = Group A	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 11: Effect of treatment on Mass per Anum within Group B.

Ranks ^a	
	Mean Rank
BT	3.28
D1	3.28
D7	3.28
D14	3.15
D21	2.03
a. Groups = Group B	
Test Statistics ^{a,b}	
N	20
Chi-Square	36.571
Df	4
P value	.000
a. Groups = Group B	
b. Friedman Test	

Since p value < 0.05, the level of significance, there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

Table no 12: Effect of treatment on Mass per Anum between Group A & B.

Test Statistics ^a					
	BT	D1	D7	D14	D21
Mann-Whitney U	200.000	200.000	200.000	190.000	200.000
Wilcoxon W	410.000	410.000	410.000	400.000	410.000
Z	0.000	0.000	0.000	-1.000	0.000
P value (2-tailed)	1.000	1.000	1.000	.317	1.000
a. Grouping Variable: Groups					
b. Not corrected for ties.					

Since p values > 0.05, the level of significance; there is no sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER REASERCH

➤ Presented study was conducted with a limited sample size, future studies with larger sample size are recommended to obtain more precise and comprehensive results.

➤ Other combination of drugs can be tried and analysed.

Fig No. 1: Instruments Needed For Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma.

Fig. no 2: In Group A-Effect of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Ksharakarma*.

Fig. no 3. In Group B-Effect of *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Ksharakarma*.

DISCUSSION

Probable mode of action of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara*

Arka being *Tikshna*, *Katu* and *Ushna* with *Kaphashamaka* action, exhibits *Arshoghna*, *Shodhana*, *Lekhana*, *Kandughna* and *Vranaropana* effects. These properties help in controlling bleeding, reducing inflammation, relieving pruritus and causing chemical cauterization of the pile mass.

Kadali (*Musa paradisiaca*) is *Kaphapittahara* and *Raktashamaka* in nature, with cooling and soothing properties that balance the intense action of *Arka*. It

supports tissue repair, reduces inflammation and minimizes pain and burning sensation.

Clinically, the *Kshara* produces early haemostasis due to its *Sthambhana* and protein-coagulating actions, leading to cessation of bleeding within the first week. Gradual shrinkage of the pile mass occurs due to *Ksharana*, *Lekhana* and *Chedana* effects, followed by sloughing and fibrotic healing within 14–21 days. Overall, *Arka-Kadali Pratisaraneeya Kshara* is effective in reducing the signs and symptoms of *Arshas*, this combination is potent enough to cauterize and shrink the pile mass, safe

enough to minimize pain, burning and tissue damage and effective enough to prevent its recurrence.

Probable Mode of Action of Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara in Arshas

Apamarga with its *Katu-Tikta Rasa*, *Laghu-Ruksha Guna* and *Ushna Veerya*, acts as a potent *Kapha-Vata shamaka*, *Lekhana* and *Shodhana* agent. The *Kshara* rapidly arrests bleeding through its *Rakta Sthambhana* and *Shoshana* actions, often within a few days. Its *Ushna* and *Tikshna* properties reduce *Kapha* and *Meda*, thereby preventing congestion and recurrence. Pain, pruritus ani, and mucous discharge are significantly reduced due to the *Kaphahara* and *Lekhana* effects, which clear local obstruction and secretions. Mild, localized inflammation induced by the *Kshara* supports natural wound cleansing and repair. A gradual shrinkage of the pile mass occurs through *Ksharana*, *Lekhana* and *Chedana* actions, followed by fibrotic healing and re-epithelialization. This process restores healthy anal mucosa with minimal scarring. Overall, *Apamarga Pratisaraneeya Kshara* offers rapid haemostasis, effective pile mass reduction, prompt symptomatic relief and satisfactory healing with minimal recurrence.

Probable Mode of action of Pratisaraniya Kshara

Arka kadali and *Apamarga Pratisaraneeya Kshara* acts on haemorrhoids in two ways

- Coagulation of protein
- Chemical cauterization of the haemorrhoidal mass

Upon application

- Immediate aseptic inflammation is initiated.
- Within the haemorrhoidal vessels the coagulation of protein leads to disintegration of haemoglobin into haem and globin. the haem present in the slough gives the discharge its colour. This is followed by ischaemic necrosis of the pile mass occurs as the blood supply to the pile mass gets impeded, sloughing off in 7–14 days. Eventually, the affected site undergoes wound healing with minimal fibrosis, leading to scar formation and obliteration of the mass.

CONCLUSION

Throughout the course of treatment, none of the subjects in either group exhibited any untoward effects following *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* or *Apamarga Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma*. The procedures in both the methods were simple and cost effective. Chi -square value is 0.40, degree of freedom is 2, p-value is 0.82. There is no significant difference between Group A and Group B in their overall response ($p > 0.05$). Based on observation and result, there is no significant difference between the effect of *Arka Kadali Pratisaraniya Kshara Karma* and *Apamarga Pratisaraniya ksharakarma* in management of *Abhyantara Arshas*.

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